

The language of history, the role of museums with the cradle of values in the spiritual and moral education of young people

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Abstract: In this article, the role of museums in reflecting the history, customs, traditions of our country, historical memory and the role of heritage in the transition from one generation to the second generation are considered incomparable historical talismans and thoughts and reflections on the activities of museums and their role in the life of young people, their development of personality spirituality. Enriched by the decision and opinions of our president on the reform of the activities of museums.

Key words: museology, museum ethics, educational significance of museums, interesting conversations and excursions, upbringing of young people in the spirit of patriotism, psychological impact, cradle of values, talisman of history, museum and society.

President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.M. The country, headed by Mirziyoyev, carries out comprehensive measures on the more complete and effective use of the existing huge tourism saloyihat, joint pilgrimage with traditional, cultural and historical tourism, the rapid development of ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic types. The priority of Tourism also assumes the systematic organization of museum activities and museum work. On December 11, 2017, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution “on approval of the program of comprehensive measures to improve the activities of state museums and strengthen their material and technical base in 2017-2027”. The fact that more than 350 museums operate in our country and serve to increase the interest of the younger generation in history with their exhibits - material evidence - also makes the demand for qualified specialists relevant. Relying on the scientific research carried out so far, it can be established that museology is a science that studies the collection of socially significant information, preservation processes, the maturation of knowledge and certain emotions through museum objects, the work of the museum, the status of the museum as a social institution, its functions and forms of their implementation in various socio - economic conditions. This article explores the Origin, history of museums, its place in social life, as well as their classification and typology.

Museums are institutions with a lively history, indicative of the past. They store material and spiritual monuments, which are reflected in the history, customs, traditions of our people. The role of museums in our culture is greater than that of benihoya, which is primarily determined by their role in the transition of historical memory and heritage from generation to generation. On the other hand, it is also the task of introducing our history to the peoples of the world through exhibits in museums. After all, the work of museums and museums is associated with the tourism industry, which in turn also affects the development of some areas of the economy of our republic. A museum is a multifunctional social institution that historically interacts with social information, designed to preserve cultural - historical and natural-scientific assets, collect information and disseminate them through museum objects. The museum documents various processes, phenomena of nature and society. Museums are also used for educational, educational and outreach purposes. Museum ethics is considered one of the

important signs of museology. The attitude towards osori atica, which has been preserved in museums for many centuries, the etiquette of visiting museums is called Museum ethics. The children's visit to the museum should be brought out through dialogue excursions that suit their psyche. The museum should teach students not only to provide knowledge about the causes and procedures of various phenomena and phenomena, but also to independently find answers to the questions posed to them, in addition to keeping them in memory. First of all, the museum takes into account the psychological state of children up to school age, the ability to perceive, think and remember the environment, mainly in children, when studying the level of perception of information. In the process of visiting the museum, initially educators of preschool institutions talk about the importance of objects in the exposition in the development of mankind. When conducting excursions through an interesting conversation, it is necessary to study their forming psychological processes, develop their creative abilities and provide children with the opportunity to use modern technologies(touch kiosks, plasma panels) in this regard. This article recommends organizing in the style of various forms of work with small-age visitors: quiz, rebus and competitions. Museums historical and cultural facts, popular names, the peculiarities of each era remain for a lifetime not only in the hearts of children, but also in their memory. Museums serve to educate young people in the spirit of patriotism, to think independently, not to look indifferent to events and phenomena, the main thing is to form feelings of preservation of their material cultural heritage. These ideas are instilled in children in the harmony of play, creativity and communication. Children get acquainted with museums and their activities, their understanding of the interconnection between the modern environment in which they live and historical periods is formed through historical and cultural monuments, aesthetic taste and the ability to admire develop, a sense of respect for another culture is decided, a passion for independent learning, the cultural heritage of different eras and peoples is growing. The role of the museum in the upbringing of children is also determined by the encouragement of their interests in culture and art. The museum serves to expand the imagination and form certain skills, to increase the observability of children. In particular, children have skills such as seeing objects of museum significance in kindergarten, on the street, in the home of their acquaintances or in the external environment, as well as communicating with cultural heritage such as behavior.in the museum, to see what is on display. As a result, children begin to be interested in museums - as a unique cultural institution. The main thing is that the disappearing culture, traditions and their importance are of particular importance in children. The museum treasure has an invaluable and unique educational impact on them. In a word, museums consist in supporting the formation and development of historical memory in the thinking of students of schools, secondary educational institutions. First president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. Karimov's speech at the opening ceremony of the Amir Temur alley in Tashkent is a sign that" if anyone wants to understand the Uzbek name, the power of the Uzbek nation, its righteousness, unlimited possibilities, contribution to universal progress, confidence in the future, we must remember the urination of Amir Temur", which also pays special attention to the activities of museums in our country.

The role of museums in the preservation of material and spiritual heritage is incomparable, especially its impact on the spiritual and moral education of young people, which further motivates young people to live in harmony with the past. The functioning of many modern museums in our country is different from previous times. As modern museums open up new facets of cultural heritage, special attention is paid not only among the inhabitants and youth

of our country, but also to the principles of interethnic friendship and harmony. Because these efforts are important in instilling feelings of respect for the culture of other peoples both in their youth. Special recognition of the place of museums is necessary in the preservation of historical and cultural heritage, its development from generation to generation, as well as in the upbringing of young people in the spirit of patriotism, a warm look at historical and cultural values. At the same time, the museum is a reflection of the attitude of society to its history and culture. For this reason, the fact that museums function in a new way, keeping pace with the times, with society and being part of society, has become an urgent issue of today. Currently, in front of museums all over the world, "what should be the Museum of the 21st century and how to attract visitors?" is a problematic issue. It was now possible not only to display the museum's objects financially, but also to promote them in different styles using a combination of modern technologies. Young people who come to the museum, the people are not an object of human educational influence, but an equal interlocutor. They have the opportunity to have a conversation with each exhibit, with each material, or rather, the museum is an unbreakable tool that connects people and history.

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